

New Strategies for Maintaining Durable Global Peace : Government consensus or declaration against the Anti-Human Holocaust

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Abstract

Over the past century, horrific genocide has occurred in Indonesia and Vietnam, resulting in the deaths of over two million Chinese immigrants and countless cases of rape against women. The properties of these immigrants were almost completely looted. However, the criminals responsible for these mass killings and their nations have not been adequately punished, and the victims and their families have received no compensation. The audacious criminal nation, Vietnam, even planned to occupy the U.S. and divide the world with the Soviet Union. Even in today's world, massacres continue to occur. In recent years, Myanmar has scammed and kidnapped more than 300,000 Chinese people, subjecting many of them to torture, gang rape, forced organ harvesting, buried alive, and massacres. The Myanmar Government and military protect these criminals and continuously attack civilian armed groups opposing these genocidal acts. It is therefore necessary for the world to rapidly build a global governmental consensus against mass killings and to issue a United Nations declaration. Strict measures must be taken to punish, hold accountable, and combat the perpetrators and nations responsible for these genocides in order to reduce the occurrence of such atrocities and safeguard global peace.

Keywords: massacres · war · world peace · ethnic conflict · strategy · creative thinking · global governance · anti-human massacre · torture · organ harvesting · government consensus · the UN declaration · punishment · compensation · emergency response · law · rape · gang rape · restrictive measures · atrocities · slaughter · global consensus · political behavioral economics · military behavioral economics · war behavioral economics

Massacres are one of the cruelest and most intolerable crimes in human history. After every massacre, humanity should have ingrained it in their hearts to prevent a repeat, but reality has been completely different.

During the thirty years before and after Vietnam's founding, China provided Vietnam with free aid equivalent to \$20 billion (1), equivalent to over 1 trillion US dollars today. However, in 1975, after the North Vietnamese authorities took over South Vietnam, they immediately nationalized all the properties that the local Chinese immigrants had worked hard for over several generations. Not only that, but the North Vietnamese forced immigrants to move to designated "concentration camps." In 1977, the Vietnamese authorities finally revealed their true intentions and a massive

anti-Chinese wave swept across the country. The Vietnamese authorities gave the Chinese immigrants two choices: either pay 12 taels [(31.25-37.8g)*12] of gold per person or be executed on the spot (1). Many people who couldn't afford twelve taels of gold were shot dead by Vietnamese military police. More people chose to raise money or secretly escape.

However, even if they paid the twelve taels of gold, the Vietnamese authorities did not allow overseas Chinese who paid to stay in the country. The twelve taels of gold were just a "bribe" and staying in Vietnam was completely impossible. A wailing and weeping elderly woman, on the verge of entering Chinese territory, recounts that her daughter was captured by Vietnamese soldiers who touched her daughter's private parts with their hands and prepared to gang rape her with ten others. However, her strong-willed daughter bit off the nose of one of the Vietnamese soldiers. In response, the soldiers brutally tortured and killed her daughter, then chopped her body into meat paste and demanded that all their expatriates eat it (1).

According to statistics, from 1977 to 1978, in just one year, more than two million refugees were forced to leave Vietnam, and one third of these immigrants died at sea or mysteriously disappeared, with the majority directly killed by the Vietnamese. The total death toll reached at least 1.5 million (1). According to later estimates by the United Nations Office for Refugees, Chinese refugees were robbed of at least \$3 billion (1). In fact, the massacre of 1.5 million Chinese people in Vietnam is just one example of genocide against humanity. The arrogant criminal country Vietnam even plans to occupy the United States and divide the world from the Soviet Union (2). Similar events have occurred in various parts of the world.

For example, in the Indonesian massacre of the Chinese people, the government, completely devoid of humanity, shockingly established rules: a reward of 10,000 Indonesian rupiahs for killing one person and a reward of 20,000 Indonesian rupiahs for raping one person (3). According to official data released by the Indonesian government in 1975, by April 1966, Suharto and his command were responsible for the massacre of approximately 500,000 Chinese (4), but the actual number is far greater. Survivors' accounts reveal that many areas where Chinese communities resided were wiped out, with scenes of unimaginable horror, to the extent that even the U.S. Central Intelligence Agency referred to the tragedy as "the most gruesome collective murder of the 20th century." In 1998, Indonesia witnessed yet another massacre of Chinese people: 100,000 Chinese women were violated in the streets, and 500,000 Chinese people were killed (5). Shockingly, the Indonesian authorities subsequently lied, claiming that only just over two thousand people were killed and less than a hundred Chinese women were subjected to humiliation.

Statesmen should remember Elon Musk's words (6): "The strength of civilized people leaves room for survival of barbarians. However, if barbarians become strong, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive." In 1967, a small Myanmar brutally massacred hundreds of thousands of Chinese (7). In recent years, Myanmar has kidnapped hundreds of thousands of Chinese, buying and selling them for tens of thousands or 200,000-300,000 CNY per person, using torture to force them into telecommunications fraud, or performing forced organ harvesting, or raping women to

give birth to babies as organ donors, or forcing them to work in mines (8-10). Those who cannot work are sold and have their organs harvested to realize their final value. Many people whose organs were removed were ultimately slaughtered. These atrocities and crimes have been protected by the Myanmar government and military for a long time.

In recent years, Myanmar has scammed and kidnapped more than 300,000 Chinese people, subjecting many of them to torture, gang rape, forced organ harvesting, buried alive, and massacres (11, 12). In the fight against large-scale telecommunications fraud and organ removal in Myanmar, armed forces protected by Myanmar military even massacred over 70 imprisoned Chinese on October 20, 2023, and buried four Chinese undercover police officers alive, despite revealing their identities (13). **This is the recent 10/20 tragedy (The October 20 tragedy) that shocked the world.** Since October 27, 2023, the Myanmar military has been deploying troops or military aircraft every day to strike against courageous civilian armed forces opposing telecommunications fraud and forced organ harvesting, and assisting telecommunications fraudsters in escaping (12). Some areas of Myanmar are undoubtedly a cruel slave society of the 21st century (12).. The northern region of Myanmar was originally belonging to China, which was forcibly combined into a loose country by greedy and evil Burmese during British colonialism. Chinese leaders, being too kind and humble, ignored the opposition of the public in the northern region of Myanmar originally belonging to China and did not reclaim the area. As a result, the greed, brutality, vileness, and dictatorship of the Burmese people led to a war lasting sixty years. In the meantime, after seventy years, the Myanmar government has proven to be inept, turning Myanmar into the world's largest opium-producing country and a major supplier of drugs to the United States, bringing enormous disasters to the world.

In order to prevent such massacres or similar large-scale crimes from happening again, it is crucial to establish a system of strict punishment and accountability, as well as a system of compensation. It is also important to establish a government consensus and a United Nations declaration against genocide.

First, war criminals and war criminal States must be held accountable for the massacre. Without punishment for war criminals, such atrocities could become a sustainable pattern and encourage other countries and organizations to attempt similar brutal acts. Severe punishment of war criminals and war criminal countries helps uphold human rights and justice, sending a strong signal to the world that acts that violate human dignity and morality are intolerable.

Second, the establishment of a compensation system is essential to provide justice to the victims and their descendants, and also to deter such acts. During the Vietnam massacre, Chinese immigrants not only lost their lives and properties, but also suffered psychological trauma and pain. By establishing a compensation system, victims can receive economic compensation to help them rebuild their lives. It also serves as a warning to other countries and organizations of the consequences of committing acts of genocide against humanity.

Third, it is meaningful to establish an incentive mechanism for countries and

individuals that actively support the pursuit of justice and accountability for war criminals and war criminal countries. Many countries and individuals around the world have made active efforts to promote human rights and justice. Providing rewards and recognition to these contributors encourages more people to focus on and engage in the cause of human rights, while also increasing international attention to genocide against humanity.

Lastly, it is crucial to establish government consensus and a United Nations declaration against genocide. Government consensus refers to the collective recognition by governments worldwide of acts of genocide against humanity and the joint efforts to prevent and combat such actions. The United Nations declaration provides a clear and comprehensive condemnation of genocide against humanity, providing a common moral guideline and framework for international action. Through government consensus and a United Nations declaration, countries can strengthen communication and cooperation, forming a united front to more effectively prevent and respond to genocide against humanity.

In conclusion, there is highly necessary to establish a government consensus and a United Nations declaration against genocide against humanity. By enforcing strict punishment and accountability for war criminals, establishing a compensation system, rewarding countries and individuals who contribute to the pursuit of justice, and strengthening international cooperation, we can prevent and combat genocide against humanity, safeguard human rights, and uphold justice. This not only protects the rights of victims, but also contributes to global peace and security. We must work together to ensure that such atrocities do not happen again.

Table S 1. Government consensus on compensation and punishment plans for war criminals who launched the "Anti-Human Massacre" to maintain sustained world peace

1	The factors that lead to war are human beings, and politicians who are evil, selfish, greedy, despicable, narrow-minded, and have a limited perspective are more likely to cause wars. From a philosophical perspective, the world must grasp the main aspects of contradictions. Statesmen have an undeniable obligation and responsibility for global peace.
2	The crimes of launching anti-human massacres, large-scale gang rapes, looting victims' wealth, or extracting victims' organs constitute crimes that seriously jeopardize global peace. Strict measures must be implemented to prevent and punish such crimes. If war criminals and war countries are not severely punished. Once the victim country becomes powerful, this counter-massacre can be carried out. Without strict punitive measures and compensation systems for war criminal countries and all criminals, any nation can repeat the massacre, slaughter humanity, carry out large-scale gang rapes, and loot wealth, making the Earth unsuitable for habitation, and causing the aspiration for peace among humanity to fall into a vicious cycle. All acts of mass killings, massive wealth plundering, large-scale rape or gang rape, or organ harvesting against civilians since 1900 that have not been

thoroughly accounted for must be fully addressed. If anyone, including politicians, spokespersons, or leaders of organizations or governments, believes that the above-mentioned crimes are innocent or disagrees with harsh punishment, and refuses to return stolen wealth, in accordance with similar principles of logic, please publicly disclose your full name, photographs, address, and the amount and location of your wealth. It is recommended that all assets be kept in an unsecured location in order to test whether individuals who may attempt massacres in the future are inclined towards looting and violence. If there is any looting of all assets and instances of rape and gang rape, etc., please declare in advance that there should be no legal punishment or compensation.

Only when past crimes are fully accounted for, and the criminals and their respective nations are severely punished, when the potential for criminal intent is suppressed and reformed, and when victims and victimized nations receive just compensation, can the world move towards lasting peace. Otherwise, the world will continue to experience warfare. Excessive leniency towards acts of genocide is a disguised form of supporting crime. The international community must acknowledge the limited level of civilization in today's world. Over the past century, China provided significant aid without seeking repayment for a certain country. However, after gaining independence, this country not only showed no gratitude to China, but also committed massacres against the Chinese people, and even had intentions to occupy the United States.

Global statesmen, military strategists, and the media should soberly recognize that economic development does not necessarily bring about civilization, and technology does not necessarily lead to civilization. Instead, they can potentially facilitate broader mass killings. By reviewing history, one should be able to understand bloody historical facts. Without accountability for these mass killings, mass abductions, widespread torture, and organ harvesting, and without a government consensus to address crimes against humanity, these criminal nations and countries with such potential ideologies, once equipped with advanced technology and rapid railways, will become more effective tools for mass killings or mass mobilizations, leading to a catastrophe for humanity. Recent events of large-scale massacres in certain regions around the world serve as typical examples, aren't they? The excessive kindness of the Chinese people, their willingness to provide aid or assistance to other countries, is highly detrimental to lasting global peace. This is not only evident in China's significant financial aid to Vietnam and Albania in the past.

Statesmen should remember Elon Musk's words: "The strength of civilized people leaves room for survival of barbarians. However, if barbarians become strong, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."

The world should wake up to the fact that the kindness of Chinese leaders has brought great disasters to the world, and the policy and behavior of China's non-interference in the internal affairs of other countries and its refraining from using force to combat mass killings is actually bringing enormous disasters to humanity. The world should also wake up to the fact that vile and evil people will

	<p>always make more demands and seek more benefits than good people. Making concessions to this kind of behavior is a great disaster for human society. Until such heinous crimes are thoroughly accounted for, there should be no major economic or military cooperation. Otherwise, it would be equivalent to providing tools for their long-term criminal activities.</p>
3	<p>War criminal countries must compensate the victim countries for all losses, and cover all expenses for the treatment and livelihood of the victims of the affected countries. They must also provide punitive compensation for the losses incurred by victims and affected countries. All plundered property must be returned to the injured state and victims, and the damaged property must be compensated for the loss.</p> <p>Any acts of atrocities committed since the 20th century that resulted in the direct or indirect killing of more than 10,000 innocent civilians or expatriates of other countries by a nation that has initiated aggressive wars, or any acts that resulted in the killing of more than 10,000 expatriates of other countries without justifiable reasons or with fabricated charges, or any acts that resulted in the massacre of a total of 30,000 or more civilians in any province of the victimized country, and have not yet received reasonable compensation, the defined criminals and war criminal nations in this consensus must immediately compensate the victimized country and victims. These kinds of massacres, accompanied by massive looting of properties, should also be compensated for the related property losses. Prioritization for compensation should be based on the number of civilians massacred, with the most victimized countries receiving preferential compensation.</p> <p>Considering the inhumane nature of the war criminals who carry out massacres during aggressive wars, the compensation standards outlined in this consensus must be in accordance with the compensation standards of 18 death and victim cases in the United States, in order to prevent the recurrence of similar events and safeguard world peace. The minimum compensation for each victim of mass killings in the victimized countries is one hundred million US dollars; for the injured, the minimum compensation is five million US dollars per person. For war criminal nations that have conducted live organ harvesting or caused permanent disabilities to the victims, the punitive compensation amount shall be at least US\$ 150 million per person.</p> <p>If a war criminal nation lacks the financial means for compensation, it must compensate the victimized country and victims with land, with the maximum compensation not exceeding 40% of its territorial area, based on land area. If the land in question involves coastal territory, the coastal waters shall be attributed to the victimized country. The war criminal nation or criminal nation shall also be responsible for relocating all residents on the compensated land, and no destruction is allowed for all living facilities and public amenities.</p> <p>Upon the enforcement of this consensus, any initiation of mass killings of the aforementioned scale shall be deemed as a war initiated by a war criminal nation without declaration, and any country has the right to carry out any armed</p>

	<p>attacks against it. All countries that have signed this agreement must terminate all trade relations and freeze all bank accounts and funds within 24 hours of such an event. The war criminal nation must compensate the victims with at least \$100 million per person, and half of the compensation received by the victimized country shall be rewarded to the leading country that attacks the war criminal nation.</p>
4	<p>If organized criminals in any country commit massacres, imprison or engage in live organ harvesting of civilians from other countries for profit, and the cumulative number of victims within that country reaches 300 or more in a year, or if 50 or more people are slaughtered at one time, it shall be considered a large-scale massacre. Once it is found that the country tolerates such crimes or fails to effectively combat them within 7 days of the emergence of such cases, and the main culprits have not been apprehended, the crimes shall be punished according to the scale of the massacre, and the victim's country may demand punitive compensation to compensate for the losses of the victims and the victimized country. The victimized country can enter the territory at any time and employ any means to combat the criminals.</p> <p>Considering the inhumane nature of the aforementioned acts, the compensation standards outlined in this consensus must be implemented in accordance with the compensation standards of 18 death and victim cases in the United States, in order to prevent the recurrence of similar events and maintain world peace. The minimum compensation for each victim of the victimized country in cases of large-scale crimes is US\$ 100 million; for the injured, the minimum compensation is US\$ 5 million per person.</p> <p>If the criminal nation responsible for large-scale crimes does not have sufficient funds for compensation, the country must compensate the victimized country and victims with land, with the maximum compensation not exceeding 40% of its territorial area, based on land area. If the land in question involves coastal territory, the coastal waters shall be attributed to the victimized country. The war criminal nation or the criminal country shall also be responsible for the relocation of all residents on the compensated land, and no destruction is allowed for all living facilities and public amenities.</p> <p>The country must publicly disclose the detailed information of all suspects and masterminds behind the scenes involved in all criminals within its borders within one month after such a heinous event occurs, including the detailed information of their immediate family members and all descendants, and freeze the bank accounts of criminals, their immediate family members, and all descendants worldwide. The confiscation of all the properties of their family members, and for the next 100 years, all criminals and their descendants must be traceable and reported to the law enforcement agencies of the victimized country whenever they leave any city or region.</p> <p>The country where the criminals carried out the crimes must apprehend all the criminals within six months. If this cannot be achieved, the United Nations or the victimized country may launch armed attacks or enter their territory to</p>

	combat them. Other restrictions on their relatives or descendants will follow the same principles outlined in this consensus.
5	<p>Anyone who signs or orders the launch of a massacre, including the President, Prime Minister, military officer, etc., must be sentenced to death.</p> <p>Anyone who commits mass murder must be sentenced to death. All criminals who kill people in a massacre must be sentenced to death, and all personal and family property must be confiscated and given to the affected countries and victims. The Geneva Conventions are no longer valid for those individuals who commit such inhuman acts.</p> <p>Any politicians, military personnel, police officers, intelligence personnel, or public officials who incite or engage in massacre must be sentenced to a minimum of 10 to 100 years in prison without parole. Dietary standards in prisons can only be implemented according to the minimum subsistence level set by middle-income countries in Africa for survival. None of these individuals, their family members, or their descendants are allowed to engage in government, military, police, intelligence, judicial, biological, chemical, medical, media or financial professions, or to hold any government position. They are forever prohibited from running for any positions as members of parliament, presidents, or any government positions. They are permanently prohibited from running for or holding leadership positions in any non-governmental organization. Those who are currently serving in the aforementioned fields must resign within 24 hours. All personal property of these individuals or assets under their control must be fully compensated to the victim countries and victims. Within 24 hours of receiving the account, individuals, their descendants and their families must report all currency assets held in bank accounts to the relevant institutions in the victim countries and to the United Nations.</p> <p>In the next 300 years, the annual consumption level of its descendants and their families cannot be higher than the average level of the country.</p>
6	<p>The war criminal country or the criminal country must compensate for property losses plundered and destroyed in the victim country. The basis for calculating the currency interest rate on property losses must be 50-80% of Warren Buffett's 1957-2022 annual compound actual return rates of 20.44% as the compensation rate for property losses. If punitive compensation is to be made, the rate of compensation should be higher.</p>
7	<p>If a war criminal or offender country lacks sufficient funds to fully compensate the victimized country or victims in monetary terms, with the consent of the victimized country or victims, a portion of the property that the war criminal country compensates can be in the form of land. However, this land must be legally owned by the country and uncontested, and it should be used to offset 20-90% of the compensation amount. The land should not be environmentally polluted, and the compensated land must be contiguous and have a minimum area of 5,000 square kilometers. If the war criminal country is adjacent to the victimized country, a portion of the neighboring land should be directly separated and compensated to the victimized country. If the land is not</p>

	<p>adjacent to the victimized country, it must border another country or be coastal. If the land is coastal, nearby islands and the corresponding waters must be compensated to the victimized country as well. The entire rights and interests of the land and its corresponding maritime area belong to the victimized country, becoming part of its territory and territorial waters. If the majority of the victims or their descendants are willing to establish a new nation on this land, the United Nations should support it. The war criminal or offender country must evacuate all residents from the compensated land, and the expenses should be borne by the war criminal or offender country. All living facilities must be maintained and not destroyed.</p>
8	<p>Abolish legal rights and procedures for lawyers to defend war criminals and criminals from countries involved in war crimes. No lawyer shall be allowed to defend these war criminals and criminals, and to defend them shall be considered as committing a grave and equivalent crime against humanity.</p>
9	<p>Reward system:</p> <p>Rewarding honourable officials is an important component in preventing or reducing the harm caused by mass killings.</p> <p>In the country of these war criminals, anyone who reports, stops, or kills those responsible for initiating a mass killing will be rewarded with 333.3-1000 square meters of land after the victorious country or the United Nations deprives the country's highest judicial authority of its judicial powers. Multiple individuals from the same family who carry out mass killings or anti-war actions will have their reward amounts accumulated. If the land area is within 666.6 square meters, it can be used for housing and will be permanently exempt from taxes.</p> <p>Any individual who reports, prevents or kills the perpetrators of mass atrocities in the convicted country will be rewarded with half of the personal and family assets of such criminals, once the victorious country or the United Nations strips the highest judicial authority of the convicted country of its judicial power. The remaining assets will belong to the victim country. If there are two heroic individuals, they will negotiate the amount of the reward. If no agreement is reached, the distribution will be in a 7:3 ratio. If there are more than three deserving individuals, the most significant contributor will receive 50% of the assets, while the remaining heroes will equally share the other 50%. Permanent responsibility will be taken for the criminals' assets and family assets. Any transfer of assets to future generations will be considered illegal, and upon discovery, any country, organization or individual must transfer all illicit assets to the designated location or account of the victim country within seven days.</p> <p>If the victorious country or the United Nations fails to deprive the highest judicial authority of the criminal State of its judicial power, and the criminal State fails to transfer bonuses and rewards for the "whistleblowers, preventers and killers of the initiators of genocide" to the relevant heroes within three months after the termination of the event or to allow the victorious country or the United Nations to transfer them to the relevant heroes, then the victorious State or the United Nations shall freeze the assets of the criminal country and transfer</p>

	<p>them to the relevant heroes within one month.</p> <p>Banks in any country or organization must not conceal the assets of criminals and war criminals from the rules in this document for any reason. Failure to comply will result in the bank's shares and the assets of criminals associated with the bank being considered war criminal assets, which will be seized by the victim country. One third of the assets involved in the above-mentioned criminal acts will be rewarded to the informer. If there are multiple informers who deserve credit, the assets awarded will be distributed in accordance with the previous rule.</p> <p>Compensation funds received by the victim country will first be allocated as bonuses proportionately awarded to global warriors who help uphold justice. The remaining 50% will be allocated as bonuses to reward the United States, the global leader in supporting justice, and all other countries and the United Nations that have filed claims against the perpetrator country. If part of the compensation consists of land, 1.5-2% of the annual fiscal revenue generated from that land over a period of 30-100 years, after being fully allocated and transferred to the victim country, will be given as a bonus to the leading nations who filed claims against the perpetrator country. If the United States is the leading country, the bonus will be awarded to the United States.</p>
10	<p>In the process of committing crimes, if the war criminal or the country of the war criminal destroys any evidence, the seriousness of their crimes will no longer be determined based on the evidence provided by the criminals, but by the victim country and the victims themselves. Any records provided by the war criminal or the war criminal country regarding the implementation of mass killings must be considered from the starting point of planning, otherwise it is considered as destruction of evidence. Anyone who directly or indirectly orders the destruction of evidence, as well as those who carry out the destruction, must be sentenced to death. Before being executed, they must wear a distinctive criminal hat and parade through the city for three days, with their faces exposed, in order to publicly display their crimes and deter present and future criminals, while also enhancing the public sense of justice due to the inhuman nature of their mass killings.</p>
11	<p>The war criminal countries that engage in massacre will be permanently deprived of any seat in international judicial institutions, voting rights and decision-making powers.</p>
12	<p>The war criminal countries that engage in massacre, their citizens, descendants or overseas offspring will be permanently deprived of voting rights and decision-making powers in any international organization, including the United Nations.</p>
13	<p>Citizens or descendants or offspring of war criminal countries that engage in massacre will be permanently disqualified from holding positions such as Chief Justice of the Supreme Court, Deputy Chief Justice, juries of the Supreme Court, Prosecutor General, Deputy Prosecutor General, members of the Public Prosecutor's Committee, Chief Prosecutors, Prosecutors, and senior prosecutors</p>

	<p>in the highest courts. Instead, citizens holding a single passport issued by the affected countries and appointed by the five permanent members of the United Nations would assume such posts.</p>
14	<p>Citizens or descendants or offspring of war criminal countries that engage in massacre will forever be prohibited from holding formal or informal positions in any international judicial institution or any position within the United Nations.</p>
15	<p>No country that has signed the consensus shall engage in trade or commerce with the war criminal nation or criminal nation until it has signed a compensation agreement with the victimized country and paid the first installment of compensation as stipulated in the agreement.</p> <p>After the signing of this consensus, or after the formation of a government consensus by the United Nations, or after the publication of a declaration by the United Nations, any country that has committed mass killings of innocent civilians or immigrants from other countries since 1900 and has not been held accountable must sign the first compensation agreement with the victimized countries and victims within six months. If the settlement is not completed, all trade between the countries that have signed this consensus and the countries that have not yet been held accountable for mass killings must be completely halted thereafter.</p> <p>Countries responsible for war crimes in World War II do not possess any right to hold other countries accountable. If there is a mass slaughter between non-criminal countries during World War II, they can offset the quantities and settle the accounts, and decide on the method of compensation.</p>
16	<p>Countries that commit war crimes will be permanently prohibited from having armed forces, self-defense forces, military aircraft, military drones, missiles, tanks, naval vessels, or any weapons with a range exceeding 5 km.</p>
17	<p>At any time, the victim country may station troops in a war criminal country, and all expenses incurred by the stationed troops shall be borne by the war criminal country. The war criminal country must provide available specialized ports and airports, with a garrison of 10,000 to 200,000 troops. If there are multiple victim countries, the distribution of troops is based on the number of victims in the victim country.</p> <p>The location of the garrison is designated by the affected country.</p> <p>If the garrison is threatened, any action can be taken. Any actions of the garrison shall not be bound by the laws of the war criminal country, but only by the laws of the victim country.</p>
18	<p>Any country that refuses to sign this Agreement shall be considered as a country attempting to initiate acts of mass genocide in the future. These countries are required to provide the United Nations and all countries that have agreed to sign this agreement, within one month, with the names and detailed information of all politicians, government officials, individuals controlling the government, and groups controlling the government that do not agree to sign this agreement or have consensus within their government. Additionally, they must provide a list of all sponsors who have provided funding to these politicians for their election</p>

	<p>campaigns over the past 20-50 years, as well as a list of payers and the reasons behind any income received beyond government-provided salaries.</p> <p>If this information is not available, all countries that have agreed to sign this Agreement reserve the right to legally freeze the assets of and to cease trade with non-signatory country, as long as the war criminal country has previously initiated acts of arbitrary mass killings resulting in the death of 50,000 innocent expatriates or civilians.</p>
19	<p>Prohibit permanent war criminal nations, their nationals, or their descendants from writing history books or any history textbooks in any country. History books or textbooks used or assessed in any university, primary or secondary school in the said country and by their descendants can only be compiled by historical experts from the victim countries. Once a violation is found, the offender must be sentenced to 5-10 years in prison. Those who privately print history books will be fined 5-10 times the printing costs and book value; if the price is not specified, the highest standard for penalties in similar printing and editing situations will be applied. Those who are directly responsible for knowing the violation but do not report it will be sentenced to 1-6 years in prison. These punishments will be carried out in the victim countries.</p>
20	<p>Completely and permanently prohibit the teaching or practice of any form of shooting, martial arts, qigong, boxing, fencing, knife techniques, stick fighting by nationals or descendants of the war-criminal country.</p>
21	<p>In investment or economic activities outside the territory of their own country, the war-torn country, its descendants, corporations, affiliated companies, or companies controlled abroad shall be completely and permanently prohibited from controlling any company in any country.</p>
22	<p>A total and permanent ban is imposed on war criminal nations, their citizens, their descendants, their corporations, their affiliated companies, or their overseas counterparts from purchasing land exceeding 1% in accumulation in any country. Any country that individually signs this agreement or this provision signifies the enforcement of this provision, which states that any citizen, or their descendants, or the company of their descendants, or their affiliated companies, or their overseas descendants, of the criminal country, who acquire more than 1% of the land in any country, will be bound by this Agreement.</p>
23	<p>The trials of perpetrators and countries responsible for carrying out massacres should be conducted in the countries affected by the crimes. Trials should not take place in the countries responsible for the massacres. The trial system should adopt the jury system of the United States, with the jury composed of ordinary citizens from the affected regions of the victim countries. There are three specific requirements:</p> <p>First, the members of the jury must be civilians from the county-level areas of the victim country that experienced the massacre.</p> <p>Secondly, these civilians must not have received higher education.</p> <p>Third, they must possess the nationality of the victim country and have never changed their nationality.</p>

	<p>Additionally, jury members must be between the ages of 18 and 75, with no age restrictions for victims.</p> <p>The jury will consist of 60 individuals, and except for the compensation amount and punishment measures specified in this consensus, any final punitive measures will be determined by the jury. Multiple victim countries can conduct multiple trials against the perpetrator country and individuals responsible for massacres.</p>
24	The legal age of marriage for anyone in the country of war criminals must be at least 22 years old for males and 20 for females in order to be allowed to marry and have children.
25	Any citizen of a criminal country, or their descendants, or the descendants of their company, or the descendants of any family company with assets or market value exceeding \$1 billion, must sell excess assets within fifteen business days.
26	All bonuses and prizes earned in anti-Holocaust, anti-biological warfare, or anti-bacterial genocide activities are exempt from personal income tax and inheritance tax.
27	<p>Once a country or individual has been designated by the United Nations as a criminal state, war criminal state, war criminal, or criminal, any institution or financial institution must publicly disclose within five working days the funds or assets held by the war criminal state, criminal state, war criminal, criminal, or criminal organization and the corresponding list.</p> <p>Any bank or financial institution or individual or organization that aids war criminal states or criminal states or war criminals or criminals in hiding assets shall be fined ten times the value of the hidden assets, and all personal and family properties of individuals involved in the crimes shall be confiscated. Only the minimum living allowance for the country is allowed to be retained. Violators and their descendants shall be permanently prohibited from engaging in any financial, governmental, legal, police, security, military, or related work.</p>
28	<p>All those who planned, commanded, or carried out large-scale massacres, war crimes, or fraudulent activities are subject to trials in the victim's country. If criminals destroy any evidence of their crimes or conceal facts related to their crimes, the evidence provided by themselves or their defense lawyers regarding exoneration, reduction of charges, or less severe punishment will not be considered or accepted. The court and jury may not believe any statements provided by criminals to defend themselves or their groups for their own benefit. These criminals or war criminals cannot have any defence lawyers, and all evidence must be based on what the victims or others provide. No country or region can hide war criminals or criminals. The country where the war criminals or criminals are from or where they are hiding must hand them over to the victim's country within two weeks. Otherwise, the victim's country or any other country can target and strike hidden criminals, including military strikes. If it is confirmed that the criminals are hiding in the country that provides shelter, the costs incurred will be borne by that country.</p> <p>If the criminal has destroyed any criminal evidence or concealed the facts of</p>

	<p>the crime, the evidence provided by the criminal or defense lawyer for exoneration, reduction or misdemeanor will not be considered and accepted. Any statements beneficial to the criminal or their group made by the criminal or their interested parties for defense can be disbelieved by the court and the jury. These criminals cannot be called suspects before the trial. Any bribery that results in the criminal receiving a lenient sentence or being found not guilty will result in the doubling of the criminal's liability. No accountability will be subject to time constraints or limitations.</p>
29	<p>Any country that has not fully compensated the victims and their families for a genocide, as well as the nation victimized by the perpetrating country, will be considered a barbaric and uncivilized nation.</p> <p>Countries that have not signed agreements recognized by the victims for the complete compensation of the victims and their families, as well as the nation victimized by the perpetrating country in the genocide, will be considered as barbaric and uncivilized nations.</p> <p>No country or company or institution shall build roads and railways for such a nation, let alone provide loans to the country or its companies, as this would be regarded as a grave political error and a nation that disregards the ethics of life.</p>
30	<p>Germany has acknowledged the crimes committed in World War II and has compensated the injured countries. It will not make any claims for the Holocaust against Germany.</p>
31	<p>War criminal countries participating in the Holocaust cannot serve as permanent members of the United Nations.</p>
32	<p>Any nuclear materials, related equipment, and facilities owned by war criminals must be readily available for inspection by the United Nations and permanent members.</p> <p>If a war criminal country conducts secret nuclear tests, any country or individual who discovers it has the right to launch any attack directly against that country, destroying the nuclear test site and all the equipment used in the tests. All personnel involved in nuclear tests must be severely punished by law. From the time the nuclear test is approved to the time it is discovered and destroyed, the country's highest leader and the individuals involved must be prosecuted for war crimes. The trial must take place in the nation of the United Nations Security Council members that first launched the attack on the nuclear test facility. The leaders who propose, approve, and lead the nuclear tests must be sentenced to death, and the execution must take place within three months.</p> <p>Their descendants will be permanently prohibited from holding any government position, whether official or temporary. They will also be permanently prohibited from studying politics, law, finance, economics, military science, atomic physics, chemistry, biology, security, or any related profession in any school or training program. Their travel itineraries must be reported when leaving any city. All bank accounts must be made public, and their addresses must be disclosed. The global public has the right to access this information at any time.</p>

33	Since 1900, no country, or its descendants or overseas descendants of the nationality involved in a mass massacre as defined by the consensus of this government shall have global media outlets that can influence other countries. If they are currently in possession, media control rights in other countries must be sold to other ethnic groups in that country, giving priority to the ethnic group that was the victim of the massacre. This transaction must be completed within three months. This provision should form a consensus among Governments and be part of the UN declaration.
34	The provisions regarding the crackdown and capture of war criminals or criminals, as well as the defense, trial, conviction, identification, and compensation of war criminals or criminals from a war-crimes or criminal state, should be included in the criminal laws of each country in accordance with the consensus of this government. Contracting member states of the United Nations should amend their respective national or regional laws within six months after the formal formation of the government consensus.
35	It is recommended that the United Nations form a United Nations consensus or declaration against the Holocaust as soon as possible on the basis of the above proposals.
36	Even if the United Nations or any influential country does not agree and release a declaration or form a consensus on the agreed content, once any affected country signs an agreement with a third country on the agreed content, it means that all the provisions of the agreement have entered into effect bilaterally, and both parties can initiate any measures stipulated in the agreement or government consents.
37	Any country that refuses to sign this consensus will be regarded as a country attempting to perpetrate inhumane massacres, large-scale rape and plundering of victims' wealth. Any country opposing this consensus will be regarded as a state that undermines international order and anti-humanity. Any politician opposing this agreement will be regarded as a politician that undermines international order and anti-humanity.

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